

MODI'S HINDUTVA POLICY: IMPLICATIONS FOR REGIONAL PEACE AND SECURITY

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the internal and regional effects of the Hindutva ideology that Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi has institutionalized. With contentious policies like the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA), the National Register of Citizens (NRC), and the repeal of Article 370 in Jammu & Kashmir, Hindutva—which has its roots in Hindu nationalism—has progressively influenced India's political and social landscape. These actions have widened rifts between communities and sparked worries about India's democracy eroding. Geopolitical tensions have increased at the regional level as a result of the Modi government's aggressive posture, tough stance toward Pakistan, and waning commitment to regional multilateralism. A wider trend toward a unilateral and ideologically motivated foreign policy is indicated by the tense relations with countries like Bangladesh and Nepal. According to the research's qualitative analysis, the development of Hindutva under Modi is threatening South Asian peace and cooperation in addition to upending India's secular democracy. In order to maintain democratic principles and regional stability, the report urges a reassessment of ideologically motivated measures.

Keywords: Hindutva Ideology, Modi, South Asia, Hegemonic designs, Indo-Pak, Indo-China

INTRODUCTION

The rise of Narendra Modi has brought about a significant ideological shift in Indian politics. The rise to power of the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), particularly through the spread of Hindutva ideology, since 2014. This study examines the impact of this ideological momentum on South Asian regional peace and security, with a focus on India's neighbors, China, Bangladesh, and Pakistan. It examines the domestic and global implications of India's ideological shift under Modi's leadership, looking at the historical context, current policy changes, and security developments. Narendra Modi's ascension to the position of Prime Minister of India in 2014 signaled a turning point. The perspective in South Asian politics and the aggressive spread of the ideology of Hindutva, a

type of Hindu nationalism based on the belief that India is essentially a Hindu country. Since the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) came to power, Hindutva which has its roots in the writings of Vinayak Damodar has been around since the early 20th century and institutionalized through groups like the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS) and the Hindutva Party (RSS)—has had a major influence on India's foreign and domestic policies. (Jaffarlot, 2021; Savarkar, 1923). India has witnessed several historic developments under Modi's leadership, such as the abrogation of Article 370 in Jammu and Kashmir, the enactment of the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA), and a marked increase in anti-Muslim and anti-religious rhetoric (Bose, 2020; Human Rights Watch, 2020). Concerns have been raised

about the broader regional implications of a religiously driven political agenda, which has not only heightened tensions within India but has also had an impact beyond its borders. Deeply ingrained religious sensitivities, ongoing territorial conflicts, and historical hostilities, especially between India and Pakistan, are characteristics of South Asia. By framing bilateral disputes in terms of communality, the Modi government's support of Hindutva may make tensions worse by reducing the opportunity for diplomatic engagement and conflict resolution (Fair, 2019). Furthermore, India's ties with other nearby nations like Bangladesh, Nepal, and Sri Lanka have been strained by Modi's ideological position. These nations have substantial Muslim populations or religious minorities who are worried about the regional repercussions of sectarian politics (Muni, 2021; Rahman, 2020). This essay investigates the relationship between South Asian regional peace and security and Modi's Hindutva strategy. It aims to respond to important queries: What impact has Hindutva had on India's international and domestic policies under Modi? What effects will this ideological change have on India's neighbors and, more generally, regional stability? In order to determine if Modi's ideological stance fosters peace or jeopardizes security in an already precarious region, this study will analyze significant policy decisions, regional diplomatic trends, and the reactions of neighboring states.

1- Literature Review

A sizable corpus of scholarly and policy-focused writing has resulted from Hindutva's rise to prominence in Indian politics, particularly during Narendra Modi's tenure as prime minister. The intellectual foundations of Hindutva, its institutional expressions, and its consequences for India's internal structure and regional standing have all been examined by academics. This section reviews key research in four areas: the ideological foundations of Hindutva, its impact on domestic policy under Modi, regional security and diplomacy, and international responses to India's ideological transformation.

1.2- Ideological Foundations of Hindutva

First conceived by Vinayak Damodar Savarkar in his 1923 work *Hindutva: Who is a Hindu?*

Hindutva is a cultural and nationalist construct as well as a religious identity (Savarkar, 1923). Savarkar's interpretation of Hindutva cast Muslims and Christians as foreigners. It sought to define Indian identity in terms of shared geography, culture, and heritage. Through the influence of groups like the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS), Vishva Hindu Parishad (VHP), and eventually the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), this ideology has evolved from a fringe narrative to a central political platform, as explained by scholars like Christophe Jaffrelot (2021).

By tracing the growth of the RSS and its influence on BJP ideology, Anderson and Damle (2018) show how these organizations institutionalized Hindutva. Cultural and educational initiatives. Their research highlights the broad ideological education that BJP leaders, such as Narendra Modi, began their political careers as RSS preachers.

1.3. Domestic Policy and Hindutva under Modi

India's domestic environment has undergone a substantial shift toward a majoritarian Hindu identity under Modi's term. According to scholars, the 2019 repeal of Article 370 in Jammu and Kashmir was a historic step that supported the Hindutva goal of uniting the country under a single identity while ignoring regional and religious diversity (Bose, 2020). Not only was the revocation administrative, but it also raised worries about human rights and increasing militarization as it represented the exercise of central authority over a territory with a majority of Muslims.

Fears of religious discrimination have increased since the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) and the projected National Register of Citizens (NRC) were introduced. By giving non-Muslim refugees from nearby nations legal preference, Hassan (2020) contends that these measures combined imply the institutionalization of Hindu supremacism and essentially redefine citizenship along religious lines. Following these legislative changes, Human Rights Watch (2020) reported an increase in state-sanctioned discrimination against Muslims, hate speech, and vigilante violence.

According to Jaffrelot (2021), the emergence of Hindutva at home has weakened secular institutions and given extremist groups in society

more confidence. Once seen as democratic pillars, the media, police, and court have all been coerced or intimidated, which has made it easier for majoritarian power to solidify.

1.4. Implications for Regional Peace and Diplomacy

India's historically non-aligned and secular approach to diplomacy has been upended by Modi's Hindutva-driven foreign policy. According to academics like Ganguly and Kapur (2019), India's deterrent stance has changed, particularly with regard to Pakistan, as a result of the ideological framing of national security and the personalizing of military strategy. In addition to being military reactions, the 2016 "surgical strikes" and the 2019 Balakot bombings were also strongly ideological acts intended to convey power and religious nationalist determination. Despite their popularity at home, Fair (2019) contends that such measures weaken strategic stability and increase the possibility of error in an already unstable nuclear environment. Pakistan has stiffened its position and limited the opportunities for diplomatic interaction since it views these actions as religious aggression rather than as typical statecraft.

Bangladesh has also voiced increasing anxiety. Rahman (2020) argues that India's CAA and NRC violate previous promises and regional trust by potentially forcing millions of "stateless" people into Bangladesh, endangering bilateral relations. Additionally, there has been diplomatic blowback against BJP officials' communal speech that refers to "illegal Bangladeshi Muslims." Concerned about Hindu revivalism or ideological imposition, even smaller neighbors like Nepal and Sri Lanka have begun to reassess their bilateral relations with India. Muni (2021) emphasizes how Modi's cultural diplomacy, including highlighting Hindu history in international meetings or promoting Ramayana circuits, has sparked accusations of Hindutva-based soft power hegemony.

1.5. Global Perceptions and Geopolitical Implications

India's democratic reversals and growing intolerance under Modi have drawn more and more criticism from international organizations and human rights groups. There is less room for criticism, press freedom, and minority rights,

according to reports by Amnesty International and Freedom House (2021). India's reputation as the largest democracy in the world has been damaged by these events. India's ties with the Muslim world, especially in the Middle East, have grown increasingly complicated, according to Ahmed (2021). While collaboration with Gulf nations is necessary for economic reasons like oil imports and remittances, Turkey, Iran, and even Saudi Arabia have expressed concern over ideological changes within India. India's treatment of Muslims and its actions in Kashmir have been repeatedly denounced by the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC). According to Panda (2020), India's strategy towards China has also been influenced by this. The emergence of Hindutva nationalism. The conflict in the Galwan Valley in 2020 exemplified this. The growing roots of nationalism and territorial claims, which can have destabilizing effects.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The ideological shift in Indian politics under Narendra Modi's leadership and its impact on regional peace and security is examined in this study using a qualitative research design. To understand the complex impact of Hindutva ideology on South Asia, a comprehensive analysis of political discourse, policy choices, and regional responses is undertaken using a qualitative approach (Cresswell and Poth, 2018). The exploratory and descriptive study attempts to highlight the impact of Hindutva on regional stability as well as the nature of its influence on foreign policy.

3.2 Research Approach and Strategy

Using an inductive methodology, the study develops hypotheses and explanations through, Collecting and examining secondary evidence. The study primarily uses documentary analysis. Understand primary and secondary texts, including government announcements, policy documents, international reports, academic publications, and media coverage, as they relate to the topic Ideological and geopolitical dynamics (Bryman, 2016).

3.3 Data Collection Methods

Secondary sources serve as the central database for this investigation. These include scholarly works and peer-reviewed journal articles; reports from international organizations (such as Human Rights Watch and Freedom House); speeches and official documents from the Indian government of Narendra Modi; news articles and opinion pieces from reputable media outlets; policy briefings and reports from think tanks (such as the Middle East Institute and the South Asia Journal); and academic books. Purposive sampling was used to select documentary sources that were appropriate for the themes of Hindutva, Modi's rule, and regional security issues (Bowen, 2009).

3.4 Data Analysis

Thematic content analysis, which enables the identification and interpretation of patterns. Narratives on the ideological foundations of Hindutva and their impact on regional peace were used to examine the collected papers. Hindutva militancy; religious nationalism and citizenship; diplomatic tensions with Muslim-majority neighbors; and regional and international reactions to India's ideological stance are some of the core themes. These issues were examined to understand how national ideology influences foreign policy and interstate relations.

3.5 Limitations

The study's reliance on secondary data limits its ability to capture an insider's perspective or real-time developments. Furthermore, both Indian and foreign media can be biased and political. Sensitive when discussing ideological topics such as Hindutva. The breadth of the study is further limited by the lack of access to sensitive national security material or private diplomatic Discussions Despite these shortcomings, the study presents a comprehensive and well-founded. Understanding the topic by integrating data from multiple credible and scholarly sources.

4. Analysis and Discussion

Under Narendra Modi, Hindutva has become a state-sponsored ideology, with profound implications for India's domestic governance and foreign policy stance. This section examines the

implications of Modi's Hindutva-based policies on South Asian regional dynamics, particularly inter-state relations, inter-religious harmony, and regional security.

4.1 Hindutva and the Militarization of Political Identity

India's national identity has increasingly been defined in terms of religion and militancy. The Modi-led military response, as well as the 2016 "surgical strikes" against suspected terrorist camps in Pakistan-administered Kashmir and the 2019 Balakot airstrikes, have been highly politically and ideologically irreligious actions (Fair, 2019). To portray Modi as a powerful nationalist leader and supporter of a Hindutva narrative, which equates to military aggression. Patriotism, these events were widely reported in India. A highly masculine and belligerent regional context where symbolic displays of power take precedence over diplomacy. This militarization of Hindu nationalism (Ganguly and Kapoor, 2019). In areas like Kashmir, which are prone to conflicts, this strategy undermines peacebuilding and increases the chances of mistakes in it.

4.2 Kashmir: Ideological Reassertion and Regional Fallout

A turning point in the use of Hindutva in the government was the abrogation of Article 370 in August 2019, which abolished the special status of Jammu and Kashmir. The ruler essentially ignores the Muslim-majority nature of the region in favor of the RSS-BJP's goal of complete national integration, a single Hindu identity (Bose, 2020). This has had serious repercussions at the regional level. Pakistan downgraded diplomatic relations and suspended trade after the unilateral action. The action was seen as a violation of bilateral agreements and international norms (Haider, 2019). An increase in ceasefire violations has further destabilized the already fragile border along the Line of Control (LoC) (Jaffarlot, 2021). Furthermore, India's broader regional diplomacy has been. Intense militancy in Kashmir and a prolonged internet shutdown have made it more difficult. has fueled and encouraged anti-India sentiments across South Asia and the Muslim world.

4.3 The CAA-NRC Controversy and Bilateral Strains

In addition to sparking widespread protests within India, relations have also been strained over the proposed National Register of Citizens (NRC) and the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA). Bangladesh, a neighbor. By providing non-Muslim refugees from Bangladesh, Pakistan, and Afghanistan with a path to citizenship, the CAA portrays their Muslim communities and these nations as oppressors of religious minorities (Hassan, 2020). Bangladesh has openly condemned the bill, seeing it as a potential source of population instability and a threat to its sovereignty (Rahman, 2020). Dhaka fears that India could force the crossing of the border by undocumented Muslims, jeopardizing cooperation on key issues such as migration and border security. Furthermore, while talking about Bangladeshi immigrants, BJP leaders' use of the terms "infiltrators" and "termites" feeds into xenophobic and sectarian narratives, further undermining bilateral confidence (Jaffrelot, 2021).

4.4 Impacts on Smaller Neighbors: Nepal, Sri Lanka, and Maldives

Previously known as "Neighborhood First," Modi's regional strategy has come under growing criticism for being a continuation of Hindutva diplomacy. For example, India's 2015 economic embargo and meddling in the constitutional process are still seen as coercive measures in Nepal (Muni, 2021). The release of a revised political map by Nepal that included Indian-claimed territory more recently sparked tensions, which many observers blame on a breakdown in trust brought on by assertive nationalism on both sides (Panda, 2020). Despite China's increasing influence in Sri Lanka, India's pro-Hindu posture and support for Tamil Hindu interests in the north have periodically sparked concerns about religious and political meddling. Similarly, because of unease with India's ideological assertiveness, the Maldives, which were once solidly in India's geopolitical circle, have occasionally shifted toward other partners (Ahmed, 2021).

4.5 Hindutva and Regional Security Complex

One of the world's most unstable and nuclearized regions is still South Asia. India's strategic

equilibrium is dangerously altered when religious dogma is incorporated into national security decision-making. The historic deterrent balance that held India-Pakistan hostilities in check has been undermined by Modi's government, which has normalized threats of punitive attacks and preemptive action (Ganguly & Kapur, 2019). India has hinted that future battles may be defined not only in geopolitical terms but also in terms of civilization by including religious nationalism into its military posture. This could result in longer, more unwinnable conflicts with Pakistan and other countries.

4.6 International Reactions and Diplomatic Isolation

India's domestic policy changes under the Hindutva ideology have drawn more attention from international watchdogs. India's deteriorating democratic norms, suppression of dissent, and persecution of minorities have been highlighted in reports by groups like Freedom House (2021) and Human Rights Watch (2020). India's reputation as the greatest secular democracy in the world has suffered as a result of these events. India's Kashmir policy and treatment of Muslims have been repeatedly denounced by the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC). Following anti-Muslim incidents and political rhetoric in India, even historically supportive Gulf countries like Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates have expressed worries (Ahmed, 2021). Therefore, Modi's ideology is having an impact on India's international alliances, especially in the Muslim world, in addition to regional security. According to the report, Narendra Modi's administration's implementation of the Hindutva ideology has exacerbated security threats, regional diplomatic tensions, and divisiveness. Under Modi, India is redefining regional ties in a way that threatens peace and exacerbates long-standing conflicts by fusing religious nationalism with foreign policy and administration. The situation in South Asia has become increasingly dangerous, especially due to its consequences. Tough for nations with large Muslim populations or long-standing conflicts with India.

5. Findings

The aim of this study was to investigate how the peace and security of South Asia is affected by the

Hindutva-based initiatives of Prime Minister Narendra Modi. Several key findings emerged and derived from the thematic analysis of secondary sources:

5.1 Ideological governance has replaced secular traditions.

According to the study, Modi has accelerated India's transformation from a secular to a Hindutva-influenced state. The ideological transformation of the state is demonstrated by policies such as the abrogation of Article 370. The CAA-NRC framework, and the encouragement of Hindu narratives in public life, politics, and Education India's national identity and domestic governance system have been radically transformed. By these actions (Jafarlot, 2021; Hassan, 2020).

5.2 Increased Diplomatic Tensions with Muslim-Majority Neighbors

Modi's Hindutva stance has strained relations with Bangladesh and Pakistan in particular. These nations have responded sharply to the withdrawal of Kashmir's special status and anti-Muslim language, threatening bilateral cooperation, downgrading diplomatic ties, and issuing public condemnations (Rahman, 2020; Haider, 2019). Traditional diplomacy is complicated by the Hindutva ideology, which portrays India's conflicts not only in political terms but also as religious or civilizational.

5.3 Regional Polarization and Strategic Instability

According to the study, India's identity-driven policies and strong posture are to blame for the increasing divisiveness in South Asia. A change from strategic prudence to assertive nationalism is seen in Modi's deployment of military action, such as the Balakot strikes (Fair, 2019). This has raised the possibility of a conflict escalation and undermined the stability of nuclear deterrence between India and Pakistan (Ganguly & Kapur, 2019).

5.4 Hindutva Weakens India's Soft Power and Global Standing

India's reputation as a democratic and multicultural nation has taken a hit. Human Rights Watch (2020) and Freedom House (2021) have reported on the decline of civic space,

religious intolerance, and democratic regression. The Gulf States and the OIC, two of India's longstanding friends in the Muslim world, have so voiced concern over India's internal policies and their implications for the area (Ahmed, 2021).

6. Recommendations

6. 1. Reaffirm Secularism in Governance

India ought to reaffirm its commitment to the secular values outlined in its constitution. Restoring domestic harmony and reestablishing confidence with neighbors requires reviewing or repealing policies that discriminate against religious minority.

6. 2. De-escalate Indo-Pak Rhetoric

Conflicts must not be framed in terms of religion by either nation. India in particular should refrain from seeing its military and diplomatic interactions with Pakistan through the prism of Hindutva. Conversation and actions aimed at fostering confidence should be given top priority.

6. 3. Promote Inclusive Regional Diplomacy

India has to use inclusive and pluralistic diplomacy to reengage its neighbors. Peace in the region depends on respecting the religious diversity and sovereignty of South Asian governments.

6. 4. Enhance Civil Society Engagement

The Indian government ought to defend the rights to protest, the press, and speech so that civil society can operate on its own. Regional leadership depends on domestic stability.

6. 5. Constructive Engage with Global Partners

The concerns raised by Islamic countries and international organizations should be taken seriously by India. Adherence to human rights standards and constructive diplomacy can improve India's reputation internationally.

Conclusion

India's political and strategic direction has undergone a dramatic change with the growth of Hindutva ideology under Prime Minister Narendra Modi. This study demonstrates that Hindutva has created profound ideological differences, both within India and beyond South Asia, despite supporters' claims that it enhances

national identity and unity. The institutionalization of religious nationalism is evident in the policies of the Modi government, which range from the abrogation of article 370 to the CAA-NRC framework. These actions have undermined South Asian security. The environment has become more hostile, tensions with Bangladesh and Pakistan have increased, and trust with smaller neighbors has been damaged. More importantly, the incorporation of religious identity into statecraft has raised the stakes and reduced the effectiveness of traditional diplomacy. The transformation of bilateral disputes into ideological conflicts. Both India's soft power and its standing as a democratic leader in the Global South have suffered as a result of its deterioration. The majority of secularist literature agrees that Modi's Hindutva policy marks a significant departure from India's post-independence secular identity. Critics caution against the divisive potential of Hindutva and its impact on regional and domestic cohesion, while supporters argue that it presents a unified national identity. Modi's ideological framing of India raises serious concerns about the future of regional security because it not only.

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